

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS ENHANCEMENT OF COMPOSITES WITH GRAPHENE AND MWCNTs

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Introduction

- The research work is to obtain a more detailed toughness enhancement effect by using MWCNTs and graphene under different adding densities.
- Obvious toughness enhancement under shearing load are obtained for MWCNTs with 1.0 g/m² density, while energy release rate of Mode I is maintained. However, the result of adding graphene is remaining still.
- Because of the different batches of the specimen material, the properties of them exist differences to some extent.
- The energy release rates are calculated according to the Russell's formula:

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{16B^2 h^3 E_{11}}$$

Comparison Under Different Adding Densities

For the first batch, the adding density is 1.0g/m², and the highest increasing rate is over 100%, which comes from the MWCNTs.

For the second batch, the adding density is 0.5g/m², and the energy release rates did not change much only with slight fluctuation.

SEM Observation

Conclusion & Discussion

- Adding graphene or multi-walled carbon nanotubes into the interlayer of the composites can improve its toughness, but it is closely related to the adding density
- It can be concluded that interlayer additives do not degrade the original properties of the composites.
- Under the same density, the enhancing effect of multi-walled carbon nanotubes is better than that of multi-layer graphene, because the extra energy required for multi-walled carbon nanotubes to pull out under the action of complex materials is more than that of multi-layer graphene being peeled off from the colloidal surface.

